

DYNAMIC SHEAR STRESS-STRAIN CHARACTERISTICS OF SiC
WHISKER REINFORCED ALUMINUM ALLOY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Dynamic shear stress-strain characteristics of SiC whisker reinforced 6061-T6 aluminum (or SiCw/6061-T6 Al) alloy composites are determined by means of a modified torsional split Hopkinson bar apparatus. A specially-designed thin-walled tubular specimen is used to eliminate the practical difficulties involved in attaching the specimen to the Hopkinson bars with an epoxy cement. The generation of a torsional loading pulse having a short rise-time is achieved through the sudden release of a torque stored in the portion of the incident bar. Reliable shear stress-strain data are presented at strain rates of over 1500/s for the SiCw/6061-T6 Al alloy composite and the matrix alloy. The experimental results show that the matrix Al alloy 6061-T6 itself is strain-rate independent over a range of strain rates in shear from 10^{-3} to about 1700/s, whereas the SiCw/6061-T6 Al alloy composite exhibits apparent strain-rate dependence.

KEYWORDS: Silicon Carbide Whisker; Aluminum Matrix Composites; Dynamic Shear Strength; Torsional Hopkinson Bar; Impact Loading

1. INTRODUCTION

Owing to the rapidly expanding applications of composite materials in the aerospace and automobile industries, the mechanical behavior of composites at impact loading rates has received much attention in recent years. Among metal matrix composites, a SiC whisker reinforced aluminum alloy composite is one of the discontinuous fiber reinforced metals which are undergoing intensive development. The mechanical properties of SiC whisker reinforced aluminum (hereafter designated as SiCw/Al) alloy composites have been investigated by several authors (see, for instance, Refs.[1-4]).

Nevertheless, the strengthening effects in view of the dynamic mechanical properties of SiCw/Al alloy composites are not yet well understood.

The objectives of the present work are to characterize the dynamic stress-strain behavior in shear of SiCw/6061-T6 Al alloy composites and to analyze the strengthening mechanisms due to the SiC whisker reinforcement. A modified torsional split Hopkinson bar apparatus [5] was developed for determining the dynamic stress-strain relations in shear of the SiCw/6061-T6 Al alloy composite fabricated by a powder metallurgical method using hot isostatic pressing. A specially-designed thin-walled tubular specimen of short gage length was used to overcome the practical difficulties involved in fixing the specimen to the loading bars with an epoxy adhesive. A torsional loading pulse with a short rise-time was generated by suddenly releasing a torque stored in the portion of the incident bar through the rapid fracture of a notched bolt. Reliable shear stress-strain data were obtained at strain rates above 1500/s for 20 vol.% SiCw/6061-T6 Al alloy composites and compared with those obtained at quasi-static strain rates. Subsequently, the static and dynamic shear stress-strain curves for the unreinforced matrix material or the 6061-T6 Al alloy were determined to investigate the influence of the SiC whisker reinforcement. In an effort to elucidate the strengthening mechanisms due to the SiC whisker reinforcement from a microscopic point of view, the fracture surfaces of the SiCw/6061-T6 Al alloy composite specimens were examined with the help of a scanning electron microscope (SEM).

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Experimental Apparatus Figure 1 shows a schematic drawing of the modified torsional split Hopkinson bar apparatus employed in the present experiments. The apparatus consists essentially of two Hopkinson bars (usually termed incident and transmitter bars), a frictional clamping device, a torque pulley and recording equipment. The specimen is placed between the incident and transmitter bars of seamless steel tubes (ASTM MT1020) with 20 mm outside diameter and 8.8 mm inside diameter. The bars are supported by a series of V-blocks that allow the bars to rotate freely in either direction. A torque is stored in the portion of the incident bar between the clamp and the torque pulley. The clamping device [6] for holding and releasing the stored torque is depicted in Figure 2. The clamp design consists of two arms with hinged bottoms that press against the sides of the incident bar under the action of the notched bolt (AISI 1045 steel). In this design, the clamp arms are shaped to match the circumference of the incident bar. The stored torque is released by further tightening of the clamp until the notched bolt breaks. Upon release of the

FIGURE 1. Torsional split Hopkinson bar system

FIGURE 2. Details of clamping device

clamp, a sharp-fronted torsional loading pulse of constant amplitude (equal to one half of the stored-torque) propagates down the incident bar toward the specimen. Simultaneously, an unloading pulse of equal magnitude propagates back toward the torque pulley. Figure 3 indicates a Lagrangian x-t diagram which illustrates the details of the torsional wave propagation in the bars. The duration of the loading pulse is the time required for the torsional pulse to travel twice the distance between the clamp and the

torque pulley. When the torsional pulse (ϕ_i) reaches the specimen, part of the pulse is reflected back (ϕ_r) and part is transmitted through the specimen (ϕ_t) into the transmitter bar.

FIGURE 3. Lagrangian $x-t$ diagram for torsional split Hopkinson bar

The incident, reflected and transmitted strain pulses were measured by two sets of 90-deg rosette strain gages (Kyowa, Type KSN-2-F3-11) mounted diametrically opposite each other on the incident and transmitter bars. The location of the strain gages was determined so that the continuous records of each strain pulse could be obtained without interference from reflections. The output signals from the gages were fed through a bridge circuit to a dual-beam digital storage oscilloscope (Iwatsu Electric Co., Model DMS-6430), having a frequency response from direct current to 250 kHz, where the signals were digitized and stored at a sampling rate of 1 μ s. The digitized data were then transmitted to a 16-bit microcomputer (NEC, PC-9801RX) for processing data.

2.2 Data Analysis The shear strain γ , strain rate $\dot{\gamma}$ and stress τ in the specimen are obtained from the torsional Hopkinson bar test records as

$$\gamma = (r_s c_b / r_b L) \int_0^t [\phi_i(t') - \phi_r(t') - \phi_t(t')] dt' \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{\gamma} = (r_s c_b / r_b L) [\dot{\phi}_i(t) - \dot{\phi}_r(t) - \dot{\phi}_t(t)] \quad (2)$$

$$\tau = (G_b r_s J_b / 2r_b J_s) [\phi_i(t) + \phi_r(t) + \phi_t(t)] \quad (3)$$

Here r is the radius, L the gage length, J the polar moment of area, c the torsional wave velocity, G the shear modulus, and t the time from the start of the pulse. The subscripts b and s denote the Hopkinson bar and the specimen, respectively; and r_s is the mean radius of the thin-walled portion of the specimen (see, Figure 4). In the above derivations, it is assumed that: (i) the plastic deformation is confined to the thin-walled portion of the specimen and does not extend into the flanges; and (ii) this deformation is uniform along the gage length. Equations (1) and (3) provide the average strain and stress in the specimen as functions of time. Eliminating time yields the stress-strain curve for the specimen at the strain rate given through Equation (2). In practice, the data reduction is carried out with the aid of the 16-bit microcomputer.

FIGURE 4. Configuration and dimensions of torsion specimen

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Fabrication Method and Specimen Configuration SiCw/6061-T6 Al alloy composites were fabricated by a powder metallurgical technique using hot isostatic pressing. The fabrication process is illustrated in Figure 5. The microstructure of the SiC whiskers in an extruded rod of the 20 vol.% SiCw/6061-T6 Al alloy composite is shown in Figure 6. The average diameter of the whiskers is about $0.4 \mu\text{m}$ and the average length of them is approximately $4 \mu\text{m}$. The chemical compositions of the SiC whiskers and the 6061 Al alloy powder are listed in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. The torsion specimen is a short thin-walled tube with integral octagonal flanges that fit into matching sockets in the ends of the Hopkinson bars. In order to prevent any relative motion between the sockets and the flanges, precise machining of each flange is needed to hold the specimen flanges against the driving faces of the octagonal sockets.

FIGURE 5. Fabrication process of SiCw/6061-T6 Al alloy composite

FIGURE 6. Microstructure of SiC whiskers in extruded rod of 20 vol. % SiCw/6061-T6 Al alloy composite

TABLE 1 Chemical composition of SiC whiskers (wt %)

Mg	Al	Ca	Cr	Fe	Co	O	H ₂ O	SiC
0.01	0.16	0.13	<0.01	0.05	<0.01	0.27	0.06	bal.

TABLE 2 Chemical composition of 6061 Al alloy powder (wt %)

	Si	Fe	Cu	Mn	Mg	Cr	Zn	Ti	O	Al
6061	0.57	0.32	0.31	0.052	1.06	0.21	0.01	0.026	0.078	bal.

3.2 Static Torsion Tests Quasi-static torsion tests were performed on long specimens with a gage length of 10 mm using a low-rate test apparatus shown schematically in Figure 7. The increase in the gage length was necessary for the accurate determination of strain in the specimen. The technique of applying a torque to the specimen consisted of attaching one end of the specimen to the clamped support bar, fixing the other end to a loading bar and then twisting it. Two 90-deg rosette strain gages (Kyowa, Type KFC-5-D16-11.) were bonded on the loading bar and connected to form a full bridge circuit. Since the deformation of the loading bar remained elastic for the range of torque used in testing, the output from the strain-gage bridge circuit could be directly converted to the torque

applied to the specimen. The angular rotation of the specimen end during loading was recorded using a one-turn precision wire-wound potentiometer (Midori Precisions Co., Model CPP-45B), driven by a pulley attached to one end of the specimen. The actual rotation of the specimen end was amplified by the ratio of the diameter of the pulley to that of the potentiometer shaft so that an angular rotation as low as 0.11 deg could be measured. The measured torque T and the angular rotation θ were converted to the corresponding shear stress and strain in the specimen by the following equations:

$$\tau = T(t)/2 \pi r_s^2 h \quad (4)$$

$$\gamma = r_s \theta(t)/L \quad (5)$$

where h is the wall thickness. The mean shear strain rate $\dot{\gamma}$ was computed from the slope of the shear strain-time plot.

FIGURE 7. Low-rate test apparatus and recording system

3.3 Torsional Split Hopkinson Bar Tests

A series of torsional impact tests was conducted using the torsional split Hopkinson bar apparatus. Figure 8 presents typical oscilloscope records from the torsional Hopkinson bar test on the SiCw/6061-T6 Al alloy composite. The top trace gives the incident and reflected strain pulses; the bottom trace gives the strain pulse transmitted through the specimen. The incident pulse is nearly flat,

with a rise time of about 50 μs and a duration of 350 μs . Figure 9 shows the resulting dynamic stress-strain curve along with the corresponding static curve. The SiCw/6061-T6 Al alloy composite is definitely strain-rate sensitive. Note that a rapid decrease in the stress level of the static curve corresponds to fracture initiation in the gage section of the specimen. Figure 10 depicts the static and dynamic shear stress-strain data for the unreinforced 6061-T6 Al alloy. A comparison of Figures 9 and 10 indicates that the static yield strength for the SiCw/6061-T6 Al alloy composite is improved by about 40 % by whisker reinforcement. In contrast to the SiCw/6061-T6 Al alloy composite, the matrix Al alloy 6061-T6 itself exhibits essentially no strain-rate sensitivity, at least up to shear strain rates of approximately 1700/s. This result is consistent with the experimental data obtained by Holt et al. [7] on the same 6061-T6 Al alloy using a compressive split Hopkinson bar technique.

Sweep rate: 100 $\mu\text{s}/\text{div}$.

Vertical scale

Top trace: 1003 $\mu\text{E}/\text{div}$.

Bottom trace: 49 $\mu\text{E}/\text{div}$.

FIGURE 8. Typical oscilloscope records from torsional split Hopkinson bar test on SiCw/6061-T6 Al alloy composite

FIGURE 9. Static and dynamic shear stress-strain curves for SiCw/6061-T6 Al alloy composite

FIGURE 10. Static and dynamic shear stress-strain curves for unreinforced 6061-T6 Al alloy

In order to study the whisker reinforcement mechanisms, the fracture surfaces of the SiCw/6061-T6 Al alloy composite specimens were examined by means of a scanning electron microscope (Hitachi, Model X650). Figure 11 represents the SEM photographs of the fracture surfaces of the static and dynamic torsion specimens. The SEM examination reveals that the fracture surface of the static torsion specimen consists of small and shallow dimples indicative of low localized ductility, whereas that of the dynamic torsion specimen exhibits larger dimples indicative of greater localized ductility. This observation is qualitatively consistent with the experimental results.

FIGURE 11. SEM photographs of fracture surfaces of SiCw/6061-T6 Al alloy composite specimens: (a) static torsion specimen; (b) dynamic torsion specimen

4. CONCLUSIONS

The shear stress-strain characteristics of the 20 vol.% SiCw/6061-T6 Al alloy composite and the matrix alloy at strain rates exceeding 1500/s have been determined by the use of the modified torsional split Hopkinson bar apparatus. The test results of this study indicate that the matrix Al alloy 6061-T6 itself is insensitive to strain-rate, at least up to about 1700/s, while the SiCw/6061-T6 Al alloy composite displays a definite strain-rate sensitivity. This is probably attributed to the dynamic interface interactions between the SiC whiskers and the matrix alloy. This view is supported by SEM observations of the fracture surfaces of the torsion specimens.

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